

Kinetics of Dehydration of Camphor and Fenchone over Alumina Catalysts

V. KRISHNASAMY*

A. C. College of Technology, Anna University, Madras-600 025

and

K. BALASUBRAMANIAN

Applied Science Division, M. I. T., Anna University, Madras-600 044

Manuscript received 15 May 1982, revised 26 September 1983, accepted 19 January 1985

Kinetics of dehydration of camphor and fenchone to aromatics have been investigated over alumina of different acid strength in a flow reactor in the temperature range 300-405°. The dehydration activity increases with decreasing acid strength and fenchone is more reactive than camphor over all the three catalysts under the experimental conditions. The reactions follow first order kinetics. Energy of activation and other thermodynamic parameters are calculated. A linear regression analysis has been carried out to obtain isokinetic relationship which holds good for dehydration of camphor and fenchone with correlation coefficient of 0.98 and 0.96, respectively.

ALUMINA has been widely employed as a catalyst and as a catalyst support for a variety of industrially important reactions, such as dehydration, isomerisation, alkylation, reforming *etc.* Dehydration of alcohols to olefins have been investigated extensively, however, very few reactions of ketone dehydration have been studied. Dehydration of acetone to mesityl oxide¹, phorone² and mesitylene³ is well known and probably the best studied of ketone dehydration. Higher ketones have been found to give condensation product⁴. In this investigation, kinetics of dehydration of camphor and fenchone to aromatics have been studied over alumina of different acid strength.

Experimental

Catalyst: Alumina A was prepared by dissolving aluminium turnings in potassium hydroxide solution. The solution was carefully neutralised with iron-free concentrated nitric acid till a faint cloud of precipitate resulted. Precipitation was completed by bubbling CO₂ through the solution as described by Selwood *et al.*⁵. Alumina B was obtained by hydrolysing aluminium isopropoxide with water according to the method described by Pines *et al.*⁶. Alumina B after activation was modified to get alumina C by impregnating it with appropriate amounts of hydrofluoric acid (40%, E. Merck) to give 5% by weight of HF in the catalyst. All catalysts were dried at 120° for 24 h and then activated at 500° in an atmosphere of pure dry air for another 24 h. The activated catalysts were crushed and ground into powder and sieved, and the 40-60 mesh fraction was selected for use.

Commercial camphor was recrystallised twice from ethanol containing 10% water, m.p. 178.3° (lit. 179.5°), and was dissolved in n-hexane. Fenchone was purified by distillation, b.p. 193°.

Procedure: Reactions were carried out in fixed-bed flow reactor at atmospheric pressure. The catalyst was placed in a pyrex reactor tube (25×3 cm i.d.). Above the catalyst bed pyrex glass beads (4×4 mm) were placed to a height of 5 cm. The tube was inserted into the furnace, a cylindrical steel tube (4 cm i.d.) coated with a thin layer of asbestos and wound uniformly with nichrome wire and heated electrically to the requisite temperature. The reactant was passed over the catalyst using a constant feed rate syringe pump that could be operated at different feed rates.

The liquid products collected for the first 15 min of each run were discarded and analysis was made only of the products collected after this period to ensure the attainment of steady state. The liquid products were mainly 1,2-dimethyl-4-ethylbenzene and *p*-cymene from camphor and *m*-cymene from fenchone, and interconversion of one ketone to another. The liquid products were identified and estimated using a Perkin-Elmer 154-D Vapour Fractometer. The column employed was a one metre squalene with hydrogen as the carrier gas. The optimum conditions for the best resolution was found to be a temperature of 115° and an inlet gas pressure of 14.5 p.s.i.

Results and Discussion

From the effect of contact time, W/F (where, W is the weight of the catalyst and F is the flow rate of

the reactant per hour) on the overall conversion of camphor and fenchone, the values of $-\log(1-x_A)$ were evaluated and plotted against contact time for alumina B in Fig. 1. The straight line plots indicate that the dehydration of these ketones follow first order kinetics. The rate of conversion of fenchone over catalysts A, B and C are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. First order plot for dehydration of camphor and fenchone over catalyst B. Temp. 335°.

Fig. 2. First order plot for dehydration of fenchone over catalysts A, B and C. Temp. 335°.

The first order rate constants calculated from the rate equation at different temperatures, both for camphor and fenchone are given in Table 1. The rate constants obtained from the slope of the first order plots are also included in Table 1. From the values of the rate constants it can be inferred that fenchone is more reactive than camphor over all the catalysts. However, among the three catalysts, catalyst A is more effective than the other two. The dehydration activity of the catalysts are found to be in the order, Alumina A > Alumina B > Alumina C.

The reactivity and selectivity of catalytic alumina change with impregnation of alkali and fluoride ions, as these ions affect the acidity of the catalyst. The former is known to weaken the strength of the sites⁷ while the latter increases it^{7,8}.

Alumina prepared from potassium aluminate may not contain strong acid sites because the residual potassium ions may poison the strong sites preferentially. As a result of the absence of strong acid sites, the undesired side reactions, such as polymerisation, cracking, etc., which lead to the formation of carbonaceous materials that deposit on the surface of the catalyst, will be minimised or even eliminated. When the side reactions are minimised, the reactivity of the catalyst is maintained constant. On the other hand hydrofluoric acid does the reverse which explains the decreased reactivity of catalyst C.

The activation energy and other thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 2. The slightly smaller activation energy values for fenchone and the general observation that fenchone is more reactive than camphor may probably be due to a difference in the polarisation of the carbonyl group of the two ketones. In fenchone the carbonyl group is flanked on either side by methyl and gem-dimethyl groups whereas in camphor only one methyl group is present. Due to the +I effect (due to Ingold) of the methyl group the partial negative charge on oxygen atom is more in fenchone than in camphor which facilitates dehydration.

The entropy of activation values corresponding to camphor and fenchone over alumina catalysts A, B and C (Table 2) indicate that the activated complex formed by fenchone over the catalysts is more stable compared to that by camphor and also the stability decreases with increasing acid strength of the catalyst.

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR DEHYDRATION OF CAMPHOR AND FENCHONE

Temp. °K	Camphor (Dehydration)			Fenchone (Dehydration)		
	Rate constant, k (sec ⁻¹) from first order equation			Rate constant, k (sec ⁻¹) from first order equation		
	Alumina A × 10 ⁴	Alumina B × 10 ⁴	Alumina C × 10 ⁴	Alumina A × 10 ⁴	Alumina B × 10 ⁴	Alumina C × 10 ⁴
573	2.7458	1.5983	1.8250	2.5666	2.2247	2.7458
608	3.8505	2.5669	3.1227	3.5250	3.1227	3.9630
643	5.0902	3.6330	4.4360	4.4361	3.9638	5.0902
678	6.3302	4.6886	6.5066	5.6660	4.8194	6.3277
From the slope of first order plot 608	3.8250	2.1110	2.5860	4.4944	3.2500	3.4720

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR DEHYDRATION OF CAMPHOR FENCHONE

Substance	Catalyst	E_a	H^\ddagger	S^\ddagger	G^\ddagger	PZ
		kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	kJ mol^{-1}	
Camphor	Alumina A	25.640	20.876	-282.1	182.52	0.0596
	Alumina B	29.610	24.746	-279.9	185.13	0.0782
	Alumina C	39.104	34.840	-261.9	184.41	0.6690
Fenchone	Alumina A	23.742	18.978	-286.1	182.91	0.0374
	Alumina B	24.820	20.056	-285.2	183.47	0.0406
	Alumina C	26.109	21.945	-281.6	182.70	0.0658

The straight line plots of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger (Fig. 3) indicates that Leffler's⁹ isokinetic relationship,

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = T \Delta S^\ddagger + \Delta H_0^\ddagger$$

Fig. 3. Plots of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger .

holds good for both the systems. The least square linear regression analysis¹⁰ have been carried out and the best fit equation for camphor over alumina A, B and C is found to be

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 615.1 \Delta S^\ddagger + 195.6$$

with isokinetic temperature of 615.1K and correlation coefficient is 0.98 (standard deviation 1.26). For fenchone dehydration over the above three catalysts, the best fit equation is found to be

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 477.2 \Delta S^\ddagger + 155.8$$

with isokinetic temperature of 477.2K and the correlation coefficient is 0.96 (standard deviation 0.34).

References

1. A. MAILHE and F. DE GODON, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1917, 21, 61.
2. V. N. IPATIEFF and A. D. PETROY, *Chem. Ber.*, 1926, 598, 2035.
3. P. W. SHERWOOD, *Pet. Refiner*, 1954, 33, 144.
4. F. M. SCHEIDT, *J. Catal.*, 1964, 3, 872.
5. R. P. EISCHENS and P. W. SELWOOD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1690.
6. H. PINES and W. O. HAAG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 2847.
7. V. KRISHNASAMY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15, 848.
8. W. K. HALL, F. E. LUTINSKI and H. R. GERBERICH, *J. Catal.*, 1964, 3, 512.
9. J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 1202.
10. B. P. KORIN, "Introduction to Statistical Method", Winthrop Publishers, Cambridge, 1977, p. 95.